

The Correlation of Limousin Bull's Fresh Semen Quality and Their Genetic Trait according to Polymorphic Secreted Phosphoprotein 1 (SPP1) and Follicle Stimulating Hormone Receptor (FSH-R) Encoding Gene Restriction Analysis

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Abstract

This research aimed to elaborate the presence of polymorphisms in Secreted Phosphoprotein 1 (SPP1) and Follicle Stimulating Hormone Receptor (FSH-R) encoding genes using Polymorphism Chain Reaction-Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (PCR-RFLP) which were then correlated to sperm concentration and motility percentage in bulls. A total of twenty samples of bull whole blood and their fresh semen were collected. The semen samples were evaluated to screen the sperm motility and concentration in standard manners. We performed DNA extractions from the bulls' whole blood followed by amplification of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene and enzymatic digestion using HindIII. The number of bands after enzymatic restriction and the results of semen quality examination were analyzed using the Spearman test ($\alpha=0.05$). The number of cleaved SPP1 gene fragments and sperm concentration showed a weak positive correlation ($r=0.231$) in contrary with the correlation to the semen motility percentage which showed a very weak negative value ($r=-0.0728$). The number of cleaved FSH-R gene fragments towards sperm concentration and motility percentage were correlated which respectively showed a very weak negative ($r=-0.0364$) and a very weak positive correlation ($r=0.0840$). Hence, there's no significant correlation of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene polymorphisms towards bull sperm concentration and motility percentage ($p>0.05$).

Keywords: FSH-R gene, Limousin bull, PCR RFLP, semen quality, SPP1 gene

Introduction

Artificial insemination (AI) in cattle aims to efficiently boost livestock productivity. The bull semen quality holds a pivotal role to the success of programmed AI in cattle industry. Several internal and external factors for instance bulls' age, breed, genetic, food and habituation as well as the semen diluent used in the semen processing chain may contribute to the frozen bull semen quality (Damayanti & Toleng, 2017). The quality of semen is scored in accordance with semen volume, color, consistency, acidity (pH), odor, concentration, motility, viability, and sperms morphologic abnormality (Varasofiari, 2013).

Limousin bulls are well-known good traits European bulls in which are resulting excellent carcass and meat quality (Chambaz *et al.*, 2003; Monson *et al.*, 2004; Pogorzelska *et al.*, 2013). However, the early selection of desired calves is relatively difficult to perform due to the lack of detection tool. The bulls must be assessed to maintain superior properties in preserving high reproductive ability as well as in producing best quality of semen. Analysis of the main genes controlling reproductive traits may provide evidences in selection of parental livestock at the molecular level (Gomez-Raya *et al.*, 2002; Pollak, 2005). Several genes including Secreted Phosphoprotein 1 (SPP1) encoding gene may control in expressing some reproductive traits (Paramitasari, 2013). The level of bulls' fertility is also related to several genes expressing reproduction hormones and receptors for example Follicle Stimulating Hormone Receptor (FSH-R).

The SPP1 proteins are believed to early activate decapitation preventing factor of bulls' sperms (Kim, 2007). They are contained in plasma, accessory glandular fluid, seminal vesicle fluid, ampulla fluid, epididymis, and sperms (Erickson, 2006). The SPP1 proteins are released by the accessory sex glands which bind to the sperm acrosome during ejaculation via α - and β -integrins in the bovine spermatozoa and both

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eventually interact with the pellucid zone of oocyte. In addition, SPP1 proteins bind to the CD44 receptor which usually participate in cell adhesion. The transmembrane CD44 glycoproteins are commonly found in sperms and bovine oocytes (Moura, 2005; Moura, 2016; Oktanella, 2014).

SPP1 proteins also function as adhesion molecules that bind germ cells to the basement membrane of the seminiferous tubules and adjacent Sertoli cells (Erickson, 2006). Primordial germ cells use integrins and extracellular matrix proteins to maintain contact with Sertoli cells and other primordial germ cells. In bulls, SPP1 proteins are expressed in seminiferous tubules, but only in the tubules containing elongated spermatids. SPP1 can also be expressed by Sertoli cells at the stage of spermatogenesis. The presence of SPP1 in the epididymis and sperm is important in regulating calcium levels in the sperm and lumen of the epididymis. The finding of SPP1 and their receptors in spermatozoa as well as seminal fluid indicates that these molecules play a role in the male reproductive system such as capacitation and sperm motility (Moura, 2005; Moura, 2016; Oktanella, 2014).

The FSH-R encoding gene encodes transmembrane receptors that interact with the follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and are found in high levels in the ovaries and testes of mammals (Arslan, 2015). The FSH-R gene greatly influences the presence of the FSH hormones which stimulate and increase the performance of Sertoli cells in spermatogenesis (Nasution, 2013).

This study aimed to observe the polymorphisms of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene in Limousin bulls as well as to find any correlation of those gene polymorphisms towards bull semen concentration and sperm motility percentage based on gene restriction analysis.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection

Twenty bull semen and blood samples were collected from selected adult Limousin bulls from National Centre of Artificial Insemination, Singosari, Malang. We collected the bull semen using artificial vaginas in the standard manner which then contained in a conical tube. Three-to-five millilitres blood samples were collected from the jugular vein which were then stored in the EDTA-containing tube. Blood-sampling protocols in this research have been approved by the Research Ethic Committee (1144 KEP UB).

Fresh Semen Evaluation

All collected semen samples were immediately evaluated to obtain the sperm concentration (using spectrophotometer) and motility values. Sperm motility was examined with computer assisted semen analysis (CASA) with IVOS-II hardware. All procedures were conducted at the mentioned centre of artificial insemination following the routine applied protocol there.

Extraction, Amplification, and RFLP

The research was conducted in Animal Disease and Diagnostic Laboratory at Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Brawijaya University. The blood DNA extractions were carried out using JENA Bioscience Preparation Blood DNA Kit (Jena Bioscience GmbH, Jena, Germany) following the manufacture protocol. All extraction results were quantitatively evaluated using NanoDrop (Thermo Fisher Scientific) spectrophotometer to approximate the DNA concentration and purity values.

Amplifications were carried out using primer SPP1_F (5'-GCAAATCAGA AGTGATAGA-3') and SPP1_R (5'-CCAAGCCAAACGTATGAGTT-3') for SPP1 (Hernawati *et al.*, 2019). Primer FSHR_F (5'-TCCCTGCCCTTCAGTGACGAAC-3') and FSH_R (5'-AGATACGCCGTCCCTT TACCT-3') were used to amplify FSH-R encoding gene (Sharifyazdi *et al.*, 2018). We set the composition mix as follows: 2.5 µl DNA sample, 1 µl forward and reverse primer (10 pmol) each, 5 µl PCR mix (5x HOT FIREPol®, Solis BioDyne, Tartu, Estonia), double distilled H₂O (ddH₂O) up to final volume of 12 µl. The amplification was set at 35 cycles in the following conditions: denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 59-61°C for 30 seconds, extension at 72°C for 60 seconds.

We prepared the RFLP mix reaction in the following composition: 4 µL amplicons, 17.2 µL nuclease-free water, 3 µl reaction buffer, and 0.8 µl HindIII. The amplicons subsequently underwent enzymatic restriction at 37°C for 24 hours. All results were then loaded in the peq-green-stained 1% agarose gel and run into the electrophoresis system. The digested amplicon bands patterns were visualized under UV transilluminator.

Statistical Analysis

Data were pooled on Microsoft Excel table before statistically analyzed and descriptive statistics values of sperm concentration and motility were calculated. Initially, Shapiro-Wilk normality test and variance homogeneity test ($\alpha=0.05$) preceded prior to determining the proper correlation test. We proceeded the correlation test of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene polymorphisms towards bull sperm concentration and motility percentage with Spearman's rank correlation test ($\alpha=0.05$) whenever the data were not parametric. All statistical calculations were performed in R version 3.3.3 (Sharifyazdi *et al.*, 2018).

In addition, we categorized the sperm motility and concentration values in qualitative classification according to a grading system (Carrol and Zamjanis, 1983). The sperm motility (%) was categorized as follows: poor (<40), fair (40-60), good (60-80), very good (>80). Whilst, the sperm concentration ($10^6/\text{ml}$) was graded as follows: poor (<200), fair (200-500), good (500-1000), very good (>1000). The number of amplicon fragments yielded after RFLP reaction was recapitulated together with qualitatively classified sperm motility and concentration values. The Fisher's exact test at $\alpha=0.05$ was performed to reassure any association among them whenever any row or column containing at least an observed number less than five.

Result and Discussion

Sperm Motility and Concentration Analysis

The bulls were kept in the standardized conditioned facilities and intensive regular monitoring. It was assumed that all selected bulls were on healthy condition and no compromised reproductive disease was observed. We evaluated the sperm concentration and motility from twenty bull semen samples according to the standard manners. All samples were pooled in a group due to limited samples available in the field.

In our study, the bull sperm motility showed relatively high variation value ranging from 41.4% to 91.1 % (**Table 1**). These values represented the sperm viability after ejaculation, reflecting bull reproductive performance. Qualitatively, it indicated that our selected bull reproductive performance varied from poor to very good in producing motile sperms. The low value of sperm motility, however, might be occurred as a resultant of unintended compromised semen handling after ejaculation or solely due to fluctuated environmental condition.

The bull sperm concentrations also showed identical trend varied from $6.32 \times 10^8/\text{ml}$ to $1.63 \times 10^9/\text{ml}$ (**Table 1**). They were ranging from good to very good quality of sperm concentration in which bull reproductive performance might be deduced from. It is believed that multiple semen collections and repeated mounting of a bull in a day may reduce the last fresh sperm concentration taken on the day of collection (Murphy *et al.*, 2018).

Table-1: The data pool of sampled Limousin bull's semen quality and the number of fragments of digested SPP1 and FSH-R amplicons

Sample number	Sperm motility (%)	Sperm concentration ($\times 10^6/\text{mL}$)	SPP1 fragments	FSH-R fragments
1	86.2%	1,090.8	2	2
2	42.1%	643.6	2	2
3	58.2%	807.5	2	1
4	29.2%	754	1	2
5	61.9%	1,632	2	0*
6	41.4%	791.6	2	2
7	89.1%	1,013.2	2	2
8	88.5%	967	1	2
9	91.1%	659	1	1
10	55.5%	737.3	2	2
11	54.8%	940	2	2
12	59.2%	995	2	0*
13	90.8%	938.6	2	2
14	87.1%	912.2	2	2

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15	91.1%	842.6	2	2
16	89.7%	808.2	2	2
17	86.6%	884.4	2	1
18	90.6%	632.2	2	2
19	36.4%	1,501.8	2	2
20	49%	1,045.8	2	1

*The value indicates no visible fragment under visualizing system

Sperm Motility and Concentration towards SPP1 & FSH-R Encoding Gene Polymorphism

The endonuclease digestion of HindIII cut approximately 290-bp length SPP1 amplicon through A/AGCTT motif along nucleotides array. In silico prediction to simulate the restriction reaction resulted no cutting site in the SPP1 encoding gene amplicon; however, several sites might contain single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) those possibly were converted to be identical restriction site sequence (Nikiforova & Nikiforov, 2011). We manually predicted the result of enzymatic restriction by searching the almost identical A/AGCTT motifs containing in SPP1 encoding gene yielding three possible fragments cleaved through two most likely cutting sites. The predicted fragments were consecutively around 30 bp, 136 bp, and 124 bp length or combination of them in case there was only one HindIII restriction site motif present along the amplified sequence.

In this study, there were at most two fragments of SPP1 encoding gene observed under UV transilluminator after performing RFLP reaction using HindIII. It evidently proved the presence of polymorphic genes in our sample population; however, the visible fragments were lesser than were previously predicted. We supposed that the amplicons might have only one cutting site or not at all. It might also be due to the low agarose gel concentration in which it was unable sieving tinier fragments, therefor some low-sized fragments run through the gel off. Additionally, it could also associate with the unintended preparation or digestion condition issues those might reduce the amplicon amount through unstable thermal degradation.

Statistically, all data groups did not meet the parametric criteria tested through Shapiro-Wilk test ($p < 0.05$) and homogeneity test ($p < 0.05$), thus we ran the Spearman's rank correlation test to see any correlation among groups. The r-value showed a weak positive correlation between the number of cleaved SPP1 fragments and sperm concentration. Inversely, a weak negative correlation was seen between the number of cleaved SPP1 fragments and sperm motility. However, no strong significant correlation was observed ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2). Figure 1a and 1b respectively depicted the correlation of number of cleaved SPP1 fragments towards sperm concentration and motility. There was no obvious trend of dots spread along the line of best fit, proving that no strong correlation was visually evident.

Table—2: The results of correlation and association test between corresponding groups

	SPP1 fragments		
	r	Spearman's p-value	Fisher's p-value
Sperm motility	-0.073	0.760*	0.007*
Sperm concentration	0.231	0.328*	0.54*

*Groups were tested at $\alpha = 0.05$

The amplification of FSH-R encoding gene yielded around 227 bp length of amplicon which subsequently underwent endonuclease restriction using HindIII. We manually predicted the presence of HindIII restriction site motif along the amplicon resulting five most likely cutting sites in which SNPs might be contained within. In case all predicted cutting site were present, there would be six fragments formed approximately measured as follows: 9 bp, 135 bp, 19 bp, 20 bp, and two other fragments with 22 bp length. However, the amplicon might contain only several instead of complete predicted cutting sites, hence, it produced several fragments in which each total length was the combination of several predicted smaller fragments. It was consistent with our finding that most amplicons were cut into two fragments with length consecutively around 144 bp and 9 bp. In addition, two samples were found with no fragment visible in the visualizing system those might be due to amplicon degradation during the procedure.

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Likewise, as SPP1 correlation to sperm motility and concentration, the number of fragments yielded from endonuclease restriction of FSH-R encoding gene did not strongly correlate to sperm motility and concentration. The statistical analysis resulted a very weak negative correlation ($r=-0.0364$) between the fragments of cleaved FSH-R encoding gene amplicon and sperm concentration. Inversely, the number of cleaved FSH-R gene fragments and sperm motility showed a weak positive correlation ($r=0.0840$). However, no significant correlation was also evident ($p>0.05$) (Table 3). Figure 1c and 1b presented the scattered plot of cleaved FSH-R fragments correlated to sperm motility and concentration. The plotted values were apparently away from the line of best fit indicating no strong correlation occurred.

Table—3: The results of correlation and association test between corresponding groups

	FSH-R fragments		
	Spearman's r	p-value	Fisher's r
Sperm motility	0.003	0.991*	0.003
Sperm concentration	-0.229	0.330*	-0.229

*Groups were tested at $\alpha=0.05$

Figure—1: The scattered plots with lines of best fit depict the correlation of sampled Limousin bull sperm motility and concentration towards the results of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene restriction analysis

Discussion

According to a research held by Oktanella *et al.* (2014) reported that the expression of SPP1 encoding gene might contribute to the calcium level regulation in sperm physiology in which the regulation alteration might end to poor sperm motility. The T-C base transition and G base deletion have been expected causing decrease of sperm motility. Moreover, a study of posttranslational phosphoserine of SPP1 protein in association with sperm motility supported so (Garbers, 1980; Tash, 1983). Giving the fact that SPP1 and FSH-R proteins physiologically play pivotal roles on sperms capacity to fertilize the ovum which are determined by their expressing gene, our findings suggested the otherwise, at least according to the polymorphic gene restriction analysis. No significant correlation was observed among the sperm motility and concentration towards the results of SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene restriction analysis. Apparently, our finding did not prove that the increasing number of fragments formed during enzymatic digestion is either strong-positively or negatively correlated to the sperm motility and concentration values.

We additionally tested the data to see any association between groups. The value of sperm motility and concentration were qualitatively categorized and plotted into contingency tables. The samples with no

fragments visible after RFLP reaction were excluded from the calculation. In this study, the Fisher's exact test resulted only a significant association between the sperm motility towards the number of fragments on SPP1 amplicon restriction analysis (p-value=0.007). The other corresponding groups did not show any association. These findings strengthened that, overall, there was no either significant correlation or association between sperm motility as well as sperm concentration towards the number of fragments produced on SPP1 and FSH-R amplicon restriction by HindIII.

However, we found some limitations those might affect the results of this study. The limited samples might not cover and reflect the condition of Limousin bull population, thus, performing study involving larger samples are recommended for future research. A control group might be useful to be set to control every apparatus working well in the same standardized condition. We suggest exploring other expressing genes using various restriction enzymes as SNPs might occur and alter the expected cutting sites sequence.

In fact, several studies reported that the presence of SNPs indeed influenced the activity of FSH-R on other cattle breeds. A study held by Sang *et al.* (2011) detected a polymorphic region of Chinese Holstein breed at 5'-upstream region of FSH-R encoding gene in which the mutation in this region might decrease the expression of FSH-R affecting the spermatogenesis activity (Varasofiari, 2013). The mutation of FSH-R encoding gene at the same region which affected was also reported affecting the Antioquia Holstein bulls' semen quality (Gaviria *et al.*, 2015), leading to assumption that the FSH-R encoding gene might be a breed-dependent gene in which the point mutations happening within affect differently among breeds.

Conclusion

According to our study, there was no strong evidence that the SPP1 and FSH-R encoding gene polymorphisms were both significantly correlated and associated to sperm motility and concentration of Limousin bulls' semen. Other gene loci could be explored to see any potential marker of Limousin bulls' sperm quality and for early prediction-purpose of superior bulls.

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